

<h2>1.SCOPE</h2>	<p>Defining the Problem and Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem Definition: Clearly describe the issue or need the proposal addresses • Current Situation: Explain the impact if no action is taken • Objectives: Set clear, measurable goals for what the project should achieve • Success Criteria: Define what success will look like
<h2>2.PLANNING</h2>	<p>Outlining the Initiative or Project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposed Solution: Explain the approach/service you are recommending • Key Activities: Outline major tasks, deliverables, timelines • Resources Needed: Identify people, technology, and partnerships required • Milestones: Highlight key stages for tracking progress
<h2>3.COSTS</h2>	<p>Identifying and Explaining Costs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost Breakdown: Detail direct and indirect costs for the initiative • Financial Impact: Highlight long-term cost savings or value for money • Return on Investment (ROI): Show expected benefits compared to costs • Funding Needs: Clearly state the funding amount requested and rationale

Stakeholder Mapping & Message Framework Template

Stakeholder Group	Role/ Interest	Key Priorities	Level of Influence	Main Concerns/ Objections	Core Messages	Supporting Evidence	Engagement Strategy	Preferred Format
Decision-Makers	Approve funding/ projects	ROI, strategic alignment	High	Risk, budget constraints	“This project drives policy impact”	Cost-benefit analysis, case studies	Formal presentations, reports	Executive summary
Influencers/ Advisors	Shape opinions, advise	Feasibility, reputation, risks	Medium	Technical risks, complexity	“Proven approach with low risk”	Pilot results, expert opinions	Workshops, briefings	Briefing sessions
Funders/ Finance Teams	Control budgets	Cost savings, efficiency	High	Long-term sustainability	“Delivers measurable savings”	Financial models, forecasts	Detailed cost-benefit analysis	Reports, dashboards
End-Users	Use the service/ project	Usability, outcomes	Low-Medium	Implementation disruption	“Improves daily operations”	User surveys, prototypes	Surveys, focus groups	Demos, workshops
Community/ Public	Impacted by outcomes	Transparency, benefits	Variable	Privacy, equity	“Positive impact for all”	Impact assessments, testimonials	Public communications	Infographics, town halls

Creating a Persuasive Narrative: Storytelling

<h3>STRUCTURE</h3>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem: Describe issue/need with data and real-world impact • Solution: Present proposed project/service as the answer • Benefits: Show tangible outcomes -cost savings, improved services, community impact
<h3>RATIONAL APPEAL - THE LOGIC</h3>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on facts, data, and evidence • Uses cost-benefit analysis, KPIs, and ROI • Appeals to logic, efficiency, and strategic priorities
<h3>EMOTIONAL APPEAL - THE HEART</h3>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on stories, values, and human impact • Creates empathy, urgency, and connection • Appeals to pride, responsibility, or community values

**Combine both appeals for maximum impact:
Lead with the heart to inspire, back it up with facts to convince.**